

***Onthophagus phalopsides* Frey, 1955, a junior synonym of *Onthophagus gonopygus* d'Orbigny, 1902 (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Onthophagini)**

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Abstract.— The dung beetle name *Onthophagus phalopsides* Frey, 1955 from Namibia was found to be a junior synonym of *Onthophagus gonopygus* d'Orbigny, 1902 described from Congo and Angola, after examination of types.

Key words.— Scarabaeidae, *Onthophagus*, dung beetles, synonymy, taxonomy, southwest Africa.

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Résumé.— L'étude des types a permis d'établir qu'*Onthophagus phalopsides* Frey, 1955 de Namibie est un synonyme junior d'*Onthophagus gonopygus* d'Orbigny, 1902 décrit du Congo et de l'Angola.

Mots clés.— Scarabaeidae, Scarabaeinae, *Onthophagus*, synonymie, taxonomie, Afrique sud-occidentale.

In 1902 d'ORBIGNY described *Onthophagus gonopygus* based upon an unspecified number of specimens coming from the Democratic Republic of Congo (« Côte du Congo ») and Angola (Benguella). Subsequently, in his « Synopsis des Onthophagides d'Afrique » (1913) the French author classified the species in his 30th group. In 1955 FREY described *Onthophagus phalopsides* from 14 specimens (9♂♂ and 5♀♀) from Karibib, S. W. Africa (now Namibia), and tentatively classified the species in the 9th group of d'Orbigny's synopsis.

The following material was studied:

***Onthophagus gonopygus* d'Orbigny, 1902**

1 ♂ labelled: white, hand: Benguela/ white, print: Ex-Musaeo H.W. BATES 1892/ blue, print: Museum Paris coll. H. d'Orbigny 1915/ red, print: TYPUS [*in* MNHN]

1 ♀ labelled: white, hand: Benguela/ blue, print: Museum Paris coll. H. d'Orbigny 1915 [*in* MNHN]

***Onthophagus phalopsides* Frey, 1955**

1 ♂ labelled: white, print: D. SW-Afrika Karibib V.1901/ white, print, hand: *Onthophagus phalopsides* m. ♂ det. G. Frey 1955/ red, print: Type [*in* MNHUB]

1 ♂ labelled: white, print: D. SW-Afrika Karibib V.1901/ white, print: ♂ /white, print, hand: *Onthophagus phalopsides* m. det. G. Frey 1955 / red, print: Type [*in* MNHUB]

The study of these typical specimens of both n, as well as the examination of a large amount of recently collected specimens coming from Namibia (Etosha N.P. I-II.1998 dung

leg. Forti & Giannatelli), show that the two entities do not differ significantly. The unique differences among the specimens are undoubtedly attributable to the degree of development of the individuals. Moreover, the variability in colour of elytra (from dark brown to black) is obviously continuous and not of taxonomic significance.

Therefore the following synonymy is proposed:

Onthophagus phalopsides Frey, 1955: 1057 = *Onthophagus gonopygus* d'Orbigny, 1902: 240
syn. nov.

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